

Magnetic Susceptibility Studies of Uranyl, Thorium and Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Schiff Bases of 2-Hydroxynaphthalidene and Substituted-naphthalidenes

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The metal complexes of bidentate Schiff bases, obtained from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and substituted-anilines, with UO_2^{2+} , Th^{4+} and VO^{2+} have been synthesised. Magnetic susceptibilities of these complexes have been measured by the Gouy method. The susceptibility values of the UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes were also obtained theoretically by Pascal's additivity method. The two sets of values were compared and the deviation from ideal behaviour has been explained on the basis of Van Vleck's equation. The deviations ($\% \Delta \chi_m$) have also been used to explain the symmetry of the complex molecule. The vanadyl complexes are paramagnetic, exhibiting magnetic moments in the range 1.85–1.95 B.M. at room temperature (300 K), suggesting that one unpaired electron is present in all the vanadyl complexes.

A large number of metal complexes with Schiff base ligands derived from aromatic aldehydes with aromatic amines are known¹. Solution stability constants of the complexes of Schiff bases with various metal ions have been intensively studied². In the present communication, we report the synthesis and magnetic properties of complexes of the type $[UO_2(LH)_2(NO_3)_2]$, $[Th(NO_3)_2(LH)_2(NO_3)_2]$ and $[VO(L)_2]$ having coordination number 8, 8 and 5 respectively, where L/LH is a Schiff base molecule as shown below:

- | | |
|----------------------------|----------------------------|
| (A) R = H | (F) R = 3'-Cl |
| (B) R = 2'-CH ₃ | (G) R = 4'-Cl |
| (C) R = 3'-CH ₃ | (H) R = 2'-NO ₂ |
| (D) R = 4'-CH ₃ | (I) R = 3'-NO ₂ |
| (E) R = 2'-Cl | (J) R = 4'-NO ₂ |

Experimental

Uranyl nitrate, thorium nitrate and vanadyl sulphate (AnalaR) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) were used. Aniline, toluidines, chloroanilines and nitroanilines (all L.R.) were purified by conventional methods.

Preparation of Schiff bases: The Schiff bases were prepared by refluxing calculated quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the corresponding amine in ethanolic medium for 2 h. Solidification occurred rapidly on cooling. In some cases the

reaction was instantaneous, but even then the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting crystals were purified by recrystallisation from ethanol. The Schiff bases obtained from nitroanilines were recrystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture. All the Schiff bases were yellow to red coloured compounds.

Preparation of complexes: The complexes were prepared by refluxing one part of the metal salt and two parts of the ligand in ethanolic medium for 2 h. The complexes of the Schiff bases with nitroanilines were prepared by dissolving the reagent in benzene and the metal salt in ethanol and then refluxing the mixture for 2 h. The uranyl and thorium complexes were yellow to orange coloured and the vanadyl complexes green to dark green compounds. These complexes were filtered, washed with alcohol/benzene and dried under reduced pressure over fused $CaCl_2$ and then in an oven at 100°.

Elemental analysis of all the ligands and complexes were carried out (Tables 1–3).

Magnetic measurements: The magnetic susceptibility measurements of all the compounds were made at room temperature (300 K) on a modified form of Gouy balance as described by Prasad *et al.*³. $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ was used as calibrating agent ($\chi_g = 16.4 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s.u.). The values of specific susceptibility (χ) and molar susceptibility (χ_m) of all the complexes were determined (Tables 1–3). The molar magnetic susceptibilities of complexes were computed using Pascal's additivity law and the values of susceptibilities for uranyl,

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF URANYL COMPLEXES

Compd. (Complexing ligand)*	Analysis % :		Mol. wt.	χ	χ		Δ_m = $(\chi - \chi'_m)$ = (χ_p)	% $\Delta\chi_m$ = $\chi \times 100$ = $\chi_m(\text{Observed})$
	Found/(Calcd.)	N Metal			Observed	Computed		
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (A)	6.02 (6.30)	27.06 (26.80)	888	0.319 1	283.36	328.72	-45.36	-16.00
[UO ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (B)	5.78 (6.11)	26.26 (25.98)	916	0.335 6	307.40	352.16	-44.76	-14.56
[UO ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](N) ₃ (C)	5.62 (6.11)	26.13 (25.98)	916	0.317 0	290.37	354.36	-63.99	-22.03
[UO ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (D)	5.87 (6.11)	26.14 (25.98)	916	0.319 3	292.47	352.70	-60.23	-20.59
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (E)	5.64 (5.85)	24.56 (24.86)	957	0.305 0	291.88	357.30	-65.42	-22.41
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](N) ₃ (F)	5.55 (5.85)	24.35 (24.86)	957	0.315 0	301.45	356.66	-55.21	-18.31
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (G)	5.27 (5.85)	24.94 (24.86)	957	0.315 0	305.57	357.66	-52.09	-17.04
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (H)	8.50 (8.58)	23.89 (24.33)	978	0.319 0	311.98	336.24	-24.26	-7.77
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (I)	8.03 (8.58)	24.67 (24.33)	978	0.290 0	283.62	335.14	-52.52	-18.52
[UO ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (J)	8.29 (8.58)	24.48 (24.33)	978	0.298 0	291.44	335.76	-44.32	-15.20

* (A)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline, (B)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methylaniline, C=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-methylaniline, (D)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-methylaniline, (E)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-chloroaniline, (F)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-chloroaniline, (G)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloroaniline, (H)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-nitroaniline, (I)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-nitroaniline, (J)=2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-nitroaniline.

TABLE 2 - ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF THORIUM COMPLEXES

Compd. (Complexing ligand)*	Analysis % :		Mol. wt.	χ	χ_m		$\Delta\chi_m$ = $(\chi_m - \chi'_m)$ = (χ_p)	% $\Delta\chi_m$ = $\chi_m \times 100$ = $\chi_m(\text{observed})$
	Found/(Calcd.)	N Metal			Observed	Computed		
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (A)	8.47 (8.62)	23.57 (23.82)	974.12	0.387 1	377.08	446.52	-69.34	-18.38
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (B)	8.62 (8.38)	23.43 (23.16)	1 002.12	0.422 5	423.39	469.96	-46.57	-10.99
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (C)	8.08 (8.38)	23.02 (23.16)	1 002.12	0.500 3	501.36	472.16	+29.20	+5.82
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₉ H ₁₅ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (D)	7.97 (8.38)	22.84 (23.16)	1 002.12	0.385 8	386.61	470.50	-33.89	-21.69
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (E)	7.94 (8.05)	21.85 (22.25)	1 043.12	0.433 8	457.72	475.10	-17.38	-3.79
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (F)	8.08 (8.05)	22.72 (22.25)	1 043.12	0.451 6	471.05	474.46	-3.41	-0.72
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ ClH ₁₃ NO) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (G)	7.78 (8.05)	21.78 (22.25)	1 043.12	0.417 3	435.29	475.46	-40.17	-9.22
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (H)	10.05 (10.52)	21.85 (21.81)	1 064.12	0.431 4	459.06	454.04	+5.02	+1.09
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (I)	9.98 (10.52)	21.47 (21.81)	1 064.12	0.451 8	480.76	453.94	+26.82	+5.57
[Th(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (J)	10.88 (10.52)	22.03 (21.81)	1 064.12	0.369 7	393.40	453.56	-60.16	-15.29

*Explanation as in Table 1.

thorium and nitrate ions, required for this purpose, were taken from the literature (Tables 1 and 2). The magnetic moment of vanadyl complexes was calculated from the relation, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_m \text{ corr} \times T}$ B.M. and are reported in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from the results that all the UO₂²⁺ and Th⁴⁺ complexes are diamagnetic, indicating that all are spin-paired. The computed values are found to be higher than the experimental values

TABLE 3 - ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF OXOVANADIUM COMPLEXES

Compd. (Complexing ligand)*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		Mol. wt.	χ	χ_m	Diamagnetic correction $\chi_m(\text{Ligand})$ (1×10^{-6} c.g.s u.)	χ'_m	μ^{eff} B.M.
	N	Metal						
[VO(C ₁₇ H ₁₇ NO) ₂] (A)	4.83 (5.00)	8.95 (9.11)	558.95	1.934	1 081.00	-347.92	1 428.92	1.85
[VO(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO) ₂] (B)	4.64 (4.77)	8.43 (8.68)	586.95	1.875	1 100.53	-371.36	1 471.89	1.88
[VO(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO) ₂] (C)	4.52 (4.77)	8.73 (8.68)	586.95	1.935	1 135.74	-373.56	1 509.30	1.91
[VO(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ NO) ₂] (D)	4.60 (4.77)	8.35 (8.68)	586.95	1.988	1 166.85	-371.90	1 538.75	1.92
[VO(C ₁₇ ClH ₁₁ NO) ₂] (E)	4.28 (4.45)	8.10 (8.11)	627.95	1.894	1 189.33	-376.50	1 565.83	1.94
[VO(C ₁₇ ClH ₁₁ NO) ₂] (F)	4.23 (4.45)	8.05 (8.11)	627.95	1.914	1 201.89	-375.86	1 577.75	1.95
[VO(C ₁₇ ClH ₁₁ NO) ₂] (G)	4.35 (4.45)	7.93 (8.11)	627.95	1.927	1 210.05	-376.86	1 586.91	1.95

*Explanation as in Table 1.

(Tables 1 and 2). These deviations are beyond experimental error and therefore are significant.

According to Van Vleck⁴, the susceptibility of a polyatomic molecule without a resultant spin is given by the equation,

$$\chi_m = \chi_d + \chi_p$$

where χ_d represent the diamagnetic term and is a function of $\sum \frac{r^2}{n}$, the radius of all electronic orbits in the molecule, and χ_p represents the second order paramagnetism, independent of temperature, which arises on account of mixing of the ground and excited states of electrons in the molecule. If the bonding of the metal with the ligand in the complex is sufficiently strong, the associating units will come very close to the metal atom, thus decreasing the value of $\sum \frac{r^2}{n}$ and hence that of the diamagnetic susceptibility of the molecule. This view is supported by the negative deviations observed by the author.

The magnitude of diamagnetic susceptibility is directly proportional to the square of the effective radius of ion. Other parameters being identical any distortion that causes deviation from close packing, results in the increase of effective radius of ion. Thus distortion in general, give rise to large diamagnetic susceptibility.

Since the bond between the component molecule is strong, it is likely to bring about a change in the symmetry of the component molecule; and hence affect the χ_p term. Thus the observed deviations from additivity is the result of the two-opposing effects, χ_d and χ_p having opposite signs. Since the symmetry of the complex formed may be entirely different from that of the constituent molecules, the change in the χ_p term would obviously

be more significant, and hence change in the molar susceptibility of the complex. Greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the contribution of χ_p term to χ_m in Van Vleck's equation. It is therefore expected that greater the symmetry of the molecule, smaller will be the deviation from additivity and vice versa.

Freed and Kasper⁶ and Lawrence⁶ observed that χ_p term is definitely present in uranyl complexes. Van Vleck attributed this paramagnetism to the matrix elements of the magnetic moment operator $\beta(L + 2s)$ between the ground state and higher states. The contribution from the spin magnetic moment is zero, since all spins are paired off in the ground state. As the largest orbital contribution comes from the two $5f_g$ bonding electrons, Eisenstein and Pryce⁷ assumed that f -electrons are responsible for the magnetism of the uranyl ion.

Belfords⁸ showed, from the orbital overlap integral calculations, that the $5f$ σ -uranium orbitals do not overlap much with the oxygen orbitals as the $6d$ -orbitals do and that considerable π -bonding also might be involved.

An attempt has been made to examine the magnetic susceptibility values of isomeric substituted complexes. A glance at the values of χ_m suggests that introduction of substituent in the amine ring of Schiff base at various positions causes an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility value. Langevin's theory postulates that a decrease in the effective positive charge will result in an increase in the diamagnetic susceptibility.

An order of increase in the susceptibility values of complexes as a result of substitution of different groups at isomeric positions in terms of Schiff

bases is represented as follows. For UO_2^{2+} ion : (i) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-methylaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-methylaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methylaniline, (ii) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-chloroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-chloroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloroaniline, (iii) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-nitroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-nitroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-nitroaniline. For Th^{4+} ion : (i) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-methylaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-methylaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-methylaniline, (ii) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-chloroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-chloroaniline, (iii) 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalideneaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-2'-nitroaniline < 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-3'-nitroaniline.

According to French⁹, if the substituent is *ortho*-para directing, the *ortho*-compound should have higher susceptibility than either *meta*- or *para*-compound, while when the substituent is *meta*-directing, the compound has the highest susceptibility values than the other substituents. This difference is attributed to the presence of higher electron density at the *ortho*-position in compounds containing two electron repelling groups *ortho* to each other and in *meta*-compound to a higher electron density at *meta*-position when the two groups are *meta* to each other. The above order indicates that authors findings are in close agreement with the above view.

Fig. 1. Plot of χ_m of uranyl complexes against Σ_z .

The molar susceptibility values of the complexes were plotted against total number of electrons Σ_z on the abscissa in the complex molecule. From the plot it appears that most of the points for uranyl complexes nearly lie on the straight line (Figs. 1 and 2) but the deviation is significant for thorium complexes. It has been assumed that the line passes through the origin. When the total number of electrons in the complex is zero, χ_m should also be zero and the straight line should pass through the origin. This observation is in conformity with

Fig. 2. Plot of χ_m of thorium complexes against Σ_z .

the one made by Prasad and Mulay¹⁰. It is also seen that all the plotted points do not lie exactly on the straight line which shows that during the formation of the complex the components have undergone deformation, which is responsible for significant deviations from additivity of magnetic susceptibility.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of vanadyl complexes lie in the range 1.85–1.95 B.M. which are close to the spin-only value¹¹ of one unpaired electron. These near normal values suggest that an interaction between vanadium atoms, such as has been proposed for other Schiff base vanadyl(IV) complexes¹² can be excluded. The higher values of magnetic moment may further be attributed to the spin-orbit coupling.

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